

A Study on the Performance of select Private Sector Balanced Category Mutual Fund Schemes in India

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Abstract

Mutual fund is an investment vehicle that pools together the funds from investors by issuing units and investing the funds so raised in securities in accordance with the objectives disclosed in the offer document. Wide varieties of schemes are being launched by mutual fund players which often confuse the investors. In this complex scenario, this study of Performance evaluation would help the investors to choose the best schemes available and will also help the AUM's in better portfolio construction and can rectify the problems of underperforming schemes. The objective of the study is to evaluate the performance of select Private sector balanced schemes on the basis of returns and comparison with their bench marks and also to appraise the performance of different category of funds using risk adjusted measures as suggested by Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen.

Objectives of the study

The study aims to evaluate performance of select Private sector balanced category mutual funds schemes on the basis of risk- return parameters and also to appraise performance of mutual funds on risk adjusted measures as suggested by Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen

Methodology

The type of research design under taken is descriptive design. For the purpose of this study the 5 private sector mutual funds in India have been selected. Five Balanced category schemes under each funds which are in operation from April 01, 2008 and those exists until March 31, 2013 were selected for the study.

Findings and Recommendations

Only two out of the five private sector balanced category mutual funds have earned a return above the average returns. Two firms have made negative returns. Amongst the private sector income schemes the maximum standard deviation is of TATA Income Fund at 18.74. All the private sector balanced category funds selected for the study have a positive Sharpe ratio. The range of excess returns over risk-free return per unit of total risk is wide. All the funds selected for the study have a positive Treynor ratio. The range of excess returns over risk-free return per unit of systematic risk is wide. All the funds selected for the study has positive Jensen's alpha indicating superior performance. There is positive correlation in case of 12 private sector funds between market returns and fund returns. Negative correlation is found in case of 13 private sector funds.

Key words: Performance Evaluation, private sector, risk and return, Bench Marks, AUM.

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I INTRODUCTION

A mutual fund is just the connecting bridge or a financial intermediary that allows a group of investors to pool their money together with a predetermined investment objective. The mutual fund will have a fund manager who is responsible for investing the gathered money into specific securities (stocks or bonds). An investor while investing in mutual funds buys units or portions of the mutual fund and thus on investing becomes a shareholder or unit holder of the fund. Mutual funds are considered as one of the best available investments compared to others as they are very cost efficient and also easy to invest in, thus by pooling money together in a mutual fund, investors can purchase stocks or bonds with much lower trading costs than if they tried to do it on their own. But the biggest advantage to mutual funds is diversification, by minimizing risk & maximizing returns.

II CONCEPT OF MUTUAL FUND

A Mutual Fund is a trust that pools the savings of a number of investors who share a common financial goal. The money thus collected is then invested in capital market and money market instruments such as shares, debentures and other securities. The income earned through these investments and the capital appreciation realised are shared by its unit holders in proportion to the number of units owned by them. Thus a Mutual Fund is the most suitable investment for the common man as it offers an opportunity to invest in a diversified, professionally managed basket of securities at a relatively low cost.

Chart – 1.2.1: Function of Mutual Fund Industry

Organisation of a Mutual Fund

There are many entities involved and chart 2 illustrates the organisational set up of a mutual fund Industry.

Chart 1.2.2: Organisation of Mutual Fund Industry

A mutual fund is set up in the form of a trust, which has sponsor, trustees, asset Management Company (AMC) and custodian. The trust is established by a sponsor or more than one sponsor who is like promoter of a company. The trustees of the mutual fund hold its property for the benefit of the unit holders. Asset Management Company (AMC) approved by SEBI manages the funds by making investments in various types of securities. Custodian, who is registered with SEBI, holds the securities of various schemes of the fund in its custody. The trustees are vested with the general power of superintendent and direction over AMC. They monitor the performance and compliance of SEBI Regulations of the mutual fund.

SEBI Regulations require that at least two thirds of the directors of trustee company or board of trustees must be independent i.e., they should not be associated with the sponsors. Also, 50% of the directors of AMC must be independent. All mutual funds are required to be registered with SEBI before they launch any scheme.

III REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bhavin A Patel (2011) conducted studied on “Performance Analysis of Selected Balanced Mutual Fund Schemes”. The study analysed 15 open ended selected balanced funds growth schemes launched by public sector, private sector and foreign mutual fund players in India. The study observed that HDFC Prudence Fund Growth, DSP Blackrock Balance Fund Growth are the top three funds on the basis of CAGR. The study also revealed that the funds have also outperformed the CRISIL Balanced Fund Index.

Rama Devi & Lenin Kumar (2011) conducted a on “Performance Evaluation of Private and Public Sponsored Mutual Funds in India”. The study analysed 340 mutual funds belonging to money market, debt, balanced and equity category of both private and public sector. The study concluded that there is no significant difference between the returns of private and public mutual funds i.e., the returns of private and public mutual fund schemes do not significantly differ from one another.

Suminder Kaur Bawa & Smiti Brar (2011) conducted Performance Evaluation of Income Schemes of Mutual Funds in India – A Public and Private Comparison”. This study analysed from April 01, 2000 to March 31, 2010. Public sector income schemes are more unpredictable while assessing the returns The study concludes that private sector leads the race.

Rama Devi & Lenin Kumar (2012) conducted a on “Performance Evaluation of Indian and Foreign Mutual Funds : A Comparative Study”. The study analysed 340 mutual funds belonging to money market, debt, balanced and equity category of both Indian and Foreign players. The study concluded that there is significant difference between the returns of Indian and Foreign mutual funds i.e., the returns of Indian mutual funds significantly differ from foreign mutual funds return.

IV OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To evaluate performance of select Private sector balanced category mutual funds schemes on the basis of risk-return parameters.
- To appraise performance of mutual funds on risk adjusted measures as suggested by Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen

V METHODOLOGY:

The type of research design under taken is descriptive design. The sample technique is simple random sampling. The leading mutual fund companies in India were selected for the study. For the purpose of this study the 5 private sector mutual funds in India have been selected. Five Balanced category schemes under each fund which are in operation from April 01, 2008 and those exists until March 31, 2013 were selected for the study.

Private Sector

- JM Financial Asset Management Private Limited
- Reliance Capital Asset Management Ltd.
- Quantum Asset Management Co. Private Ltd
- Tata Asset Management Limited
- Sundaram BNP Paribas Asset Management Company Limited

Method of data collection

Secondary data has been collected from amfi website, websites of the companies and from the fact sheet of the schemes.

Tool used for analysis:

- Risk- returns parameters.

Return: The daily log returns are computed on the basis of the NAV of the different schemes and returns in the market index are calculated. The log return from a mutual fund scheme (Rst) at time t, given in Equation-1, is as follows:

$$R = (\text{NAV}_t / \text{NAV}_{t-1})$$

Risk adjusted measures as suggested by Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen

Sharpe Ratio: It is calculated by subtracting the risk-free rate of return (return on government securities) from the rate of return for a portfolio and dividing the result by the standard deviation of the portfolio returns.

Sharpe Ratio = $\frac{R_p - R_f}{\sigma_p}$ Where R_p = Expected portfolio rate of return R_f = Risk free rate of return σ_p = Portfolio

$$\text{Sharpe's index} = (R_p - R_f) \div \sigma_p$$

R_p = Portfolio return over a period

R_f = Risk-free return over a period

σ_p = Total risk, standard deviation of portfolio return

Treynor Ratio: it measures returns earned in excess of that which could have been earned on a risk-less investment per each unit of market risk. Treynor Ratio = $\frac{R_p - R_f}{\beta_p}$ Where R_p = Expected portfolio rate of return R_f = Risk free rate of return β = beta of the portfolio Thus, the Treynor ratio is a risk-adjusted measure of return based on systematic risk. The difference between the Sharpe ratio and the Treynor ratio is the use of beta instead of standard deviation as the measurement of risk / volatility

$$\text{Treynor's index} = (R_p - R_f) \div \beta_p$$

Where,

R_p = Portfolio return over a period

R_f = Risk-free return over a period

β_p = Market-risk, beta coefficient

Jensen's alpha: A risk-adjusted performance measure that represents the average return on a portfolio over and above that predicted by the capital asset pricing model (CAPM), given the portfolio's beta and the average market return. This is the portfolio's alpha. In fact, the concept is sometimes referred to as "Jensen's alpha."

Jensen's Measure is calculated as:

$$\alpha_p = R_p - [R_f + \beta_p (R_m - R_f)]$$

Where : —

R_p = Expected total portfolio return

R_f = Risk free rate

β_p = Beta of the portfolio

R_m = Expected market return

VI ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This section deals with the analysis and interpretation of the secondary data collected for the purpose of the study.

Private Sector Balanced Category Funds

TABLE I JM Financial Asset Management Private Limited

S. No	Private balance category fund	Returns (%)	Risk	Risk/Return	Sharpe	Treynor	Jensen
1	JM Balanced Mutual	7.0	12.29	12.09	3.44	97.66	11.55
2	JM Basic Fund	6.8	2.11	1.63	1.12	19.26	1.26
3	JM Core 11 Fund	4.8	15.63	0.34	0.08	-0.90	2.00
4	JM Multi Strategy	7.01	1.47	4.13	3.40	35.28	3.62
5	JM Tax Gain Fund	6.2	0.44	0.61	0.92	-10.07	0.88

The returns of JM Financial Asset Management Private Limited ranges from 4.8 to 7.01; risk ranges from 0.44 to 15.63; Sharpe Ratio ranges from 0.08 to 3.44; Treynor Ratio ranges from -10.07 to 97.66 and Jensen measure ranges from 0.88 to 11.55.

TABLE II Quantum Asset Management Co. Private Ltd.

S. No	Private balance category fund	Returns (%)	Risk	Risk/Return	Sharpe	Treynor	Jensen
1	Quantum Index Fund	1.3	11.36	302.67	0.89	8.90	154.79
2	Quantum Long Term Equity Fund	7.8	11.30	3.48	1.03	11.4	2.15
3	Quantum Tax Saving Fund	10.09	69.17	10.714	1.28	12.97	7.11
4	Quantum Equity Fund of Funds	7.8	9.52	5.80	1.88	18.82	4.46
5	Quantum Liquid Fund	8.7	26.37	5.59	1.08	10.77	3.33

The returns of Quantum Asset Management Co. Private Ltd. ranges from 1.3 to 10.09; risk ranges from 9.52 to 69.17; Sharpe Ratio ranges from 0.89 to 1.88; Treynor Ratio ranges from 8.90 to 18.82 and Jensen measure ranges from 2.15 to 154.79.

TABLE III Reliance Capital Asset Management Ltd

S. No	Private balance category fund	Returns (%)	Risk	Risk/Return	Sharpe	Treynor	Jensen
1	Reliance Institutional Dividend Plan	4.9	14.50	7.99	2.10	-23.20	9.49
2	Reliance Retail Dividend Plan	7.5	7.79	2.99	1.07	12.52	1.95
3	Reliance Banking Fund - Bonus Plan	2.08	9.09	47.38	0.88	9.13	24.79
4	Reliance Power Sector Fund - Institutional Dividend Plan	13.53	6.66	17.022	1.06	10.52	9.98
5	Reliance Dual Advantage Fixed Tenure Fund Plan A - Dividend Plan	7.13	2.10	2.39	1.65	16.50	1.76

The returns of Reliance Capital Asset Management Ltd ranges from 2.08 to 13.53; risk ranges from 2.10 to 9.09; Sharpe Ratio ranges from 0.88 to 2.10; Treynor Ratio ranges from -23.20 to 16.50 and Jensen measure ranges from 1.76 to 24.79.

TABLE IV Sundaram BNP Paribas Asset Management Company Limited

S. No	Private balance category fund	Returns (%)	Risk	Risk/Return	Sharpe	Treynor	Jensen
1	Sudaram Rural India Fund	5.4	8.02	8.91	3.14	-38.14	9.92
2	Sundaram Energy Opportunity Fund	6.6	1.37	1.1	0.95	47.28	1.01
3	Sundaram Entertainment Opportunity Fund	6.4	1.50	3.57	2.91	-648.08	3.59
4	Sundaram Equity Multipiler	6.8	1.81	3.82	2.83	52.05	3.50
5	Sundaram Equity Plus	7.1	2.34	2.46	1.60	16.17	1.79

The returns of Sundaram BNP Paribas Asset Management Company Limited ranges from 5.4 to 7.1; risk ranges from 1.37 to 8.02; Sharpe Ratio ranges from 0.95 to 3.14; Treynor Ratio ranges from -168.08 to 47.28 and Jensen measure ranges from 1.01 to 9.92.

TABLE V Tata Asset Management Limited

S. No	Private balance category fund	Returns (%)	Risk	Risk/Return	Sharpe	Treynor	Jensen
1	Tata Equity Management	4.18	32.31	6.30	1.10	-11.83	8.62
2	Tata Dividend Yield Fund	13.8	289.41	15.54	0.91	9.14	8.14
3	Tata Equity Opportunities Fund-Dividend	9.2	42.22	9.11	1.40	14.25	6.33
4	Tata Ethical Fund-Dividend	15.13	388.69	20.19	1.02	10.18	11.56
5	Tata Pure Equity Fund-Dividend Option	13.4	257.81	14.89	0.92	9.35	7.96

The returns of Tata Asset Management Limited ranges from 4.18 to 15.13; risk ranges from 32.31 to 388.69; Sharpe Ratio ranges from 0.91 to 1.40; Treynor Ratio ranges from -11.83 to 14.25 and Jensen measure ranges from 6.33 to 11.56.

TABLE VI Comparative Table for Yearly Average NAV of the Schemes

Mutual Funds/Year	2008-09		2009-10		2010-11		2011-12		2012-13	
	Avg NAV	Growth %								
Private Sector Balanced Category Funds										
JM	10.67		10.81	1.31	11.24	3.98	10.47	-6.9	11.25	7.45
QUANTUM	12.41		16.14	30.06	17.95	11.21	18.15	1.1	18.75	3.31
RELIANCE	10.55		10.62	0.66	10.45	-1.60	9.98	-4.5	10.14	1.60
SUNDARAM	13.08		16.77	28.21	18.29	9.06	18.74	2.5	20.19	7.74
TATA	13.1		12.09	-7.71	10.98	-9.18	10.5	-4.4	10.86	3.43
AVERAGE RETURNS	59.81		66.43	11.06	68.91	3.73	67.84	-1.55	71.19	4.93

The above table shows the yearly average of the NAV of the private sector schemes selected for the study. The returns show a fluctuating trend. The performance is satisfactory.

TABLE VII Comparative Total Return (%) since April 01, 2008 up to 31April, 2013

Schemes	Total return	Rank
Private Sector Balanced Category Funds		
JM	5.44	3
Quantum	51.09	2
Reliance	-3.89	4
Sundaram	54.36	1
TATA	-17.10	5
Average Returns	19.03	

Only two out of the five private sector balanced category mutual funds have earned a return above the average returns. Two firms have made negative returns.

TABLE VIII Comparative table for Standard Deviations of fund returns

Schemes	Standard deviation
Private Sector Balanced Category Funds	
JM	0.53
Quantum	0.22
Reliance	0.46
Sundaram	0.29
TATA	18.74

Amongst the private sector income schemes the maximum standard deviation is of TATA Income Fund at 18.74.

CALCULATION OF SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN’S APLHA

While analysing a fund's historical returns, it is also imperative to look at its risk exposure, or in other words, consider the fund's risk-adjusted returns. The two quantitative ratios-Sharpe and Treynor-come handy as these are the measures of risk-adjusted returns. The two ratios measure how much a fund has earned over the risk-free rate (also known as excess returns) relative to the risk it is exposed.

TABLE IX Sharpe Ratio

Private Sector Balanced Category Funds	SHARPE	Rank
JM Balanced Fund	0.08	1
JM Multi Strategy	0.86	2
Sundaram Rural India Fund	0.88	3
Sundaram Entertainment Opportunity Fund	0.89	4
Sundaram Equity Multiplier	0.91	5
Reliance Annual Interval Fund - Series I - Institutional Dividend Plan	0.95	6
Quantum Equity Fund Of Funds	1.02	7
Reliance Dual Advantage Fixed Tenure Fund Plan A - Dividend Plan	1.06	8
Sundaram Equity Plus	1.12	9
Tata Equity Opportunities Fund-A Dividend	1.16	10
Quantum TAX SAVING FUND	1.29	11
Reliance annual fund plan	1.41	12
JM Basic Fund	1.6	13
Tata Equity Management	1.62	14
Quantum Liquid Fund	1.62	15
Reliance Annual Interval Fund - Series I - Institutional Dividend Plan	1.65	16
Reliance Diversified Power Sector Fund - Institutional Dividend Plan	1.7	17
Quantum Long Term Equity Fund	1.88	18
Tata Ethical Fund-Dividend	1.97	19
Sundaram Energy Opportunity Fund	2.2	20
Tata Pure Equity Fund-Dividend Option	2.83	21
Tata Dividend Yield Fund	2.91	22
Quantum Index Fund	3.14	23
Reliance Banking Fund - Bonus Plan	3.4	24
JM Core 11 Fund	4.17	25

It is clear from the above table that all the funds selected for the study have a positive Sharpe ratio. The range of excess returns over risk-free return per unit of total risk is wide.

TABLE X TREYNOR RATIO

Private Sector Balanced Category Funds	TREYNOR	Rank
JM Balanced Mutual	-108.72	1
Sundaram Equity Multiplier	-24.96	2
JM Multi Strategy	-23.201	3
Sundaram Energy Opportunity Fund	-21.23	4
JM Basic Fund	-11.83	5
Quantum Equity Fund Of Funds	-10.07	6
Reliance Dual Advantage Fixed Tenure Fund Plan A - Dividend Plan	9.13	7
Sundaram Equity Plus	9.14	8
Tata Equity Opportunities Fund-Dividend	10.18	9
Quantum Tax Saving Fund	12.02	10
Reliance Retail Dividend Plan	12.52	12
Quantum Long Term Equity Fund	13.9	13
Quantum Liquid Fund	14.23	14
Reliance Power Sector Fund - Institutional Dividend Plan	14.25	15
Tata Ethical Fund-Dividend	14.86	16
Tata Pure Equity Fund-Dividend Option	15.14	17
Tata Dividend Yield Fund	16.17	18
Quantum Index Fund	16.5	19
JM Core 11 Fund	17.29	20
JM Tax Gain Fund	18.82	21
Tata Equity Management	19.2	22
Reliance Institutional Dividend Plan	47.28	23
Sundaram Rural India Fund	68.51	24
Sundaram Entertainment Opportunity Fund	234.12	25

It is clear from the above table that all the funds selected for the study have a positive Treynor ratio. The range of excess returns over risk-free return per unit of systematic risk is wide.

TABLE XI JENSEN'S ALPHA

Private Sector Balanced Category Funds	Jensen's Alpha	Rank
JM Core 11 Fund	0.08	1
Reliance Banking Fund - Bonus Plan	0.88	2
Quantum Intex Fund	0.89	3
Tata Dividend Yield Fund	0.91	4
JM Tax Gain Fund	0.92	5
Tata Pure Equity Fund-Dividend Option	0.92	6
Sundaram Energy Opportunity Fund	0.95	7
Tata Ethical Fund-Dividend	1.02	8
Quantum Long Term Equity Fund	1.03	9
Reliance Power Sector Fund - Institutional Dividend Plan	1.06	10
Reliance Retail Dividend Plan	1.07	12
Quantum Liquid Fund	1.08	13
Tata Equity Management	1.1	14
JM Basic Fund	1.12	15
Quantum Tax Saving Fund	1.28	16
Tata Equity Opportunities Fund-Dividend	1.4	17
Reliance Dual Advantage Fixed Tenure Fund Plan A - Dividend Plan	1.65	18
Quantum Equity Fund Of Funds	1.88	19
Reliance Institutional Dividend Plan	2.1	20
Sundaram Equity Multiplier	2.83	21
Sundaram Entertainment Opportunity Fund	2.91	22
Sundaram Rural India Fund	3.14	23
JM Multi Strategy	3.4	24
JM Balanced Mutual	3.44	25

It is evident from the above table that all the funds selected for the study has positive Jensen's alpha indicating superior performance.

TABLE XII CORRELATION BETWEEN MARKET RETURN AND INDEX RETURN

S.No	Private Sector Balanced Category Funds	Correlation
1	Sundaram Entertainment Opportunity Fund	-0.73
2	Sundaram Rural India Fund	0.30
3	Reliance Institutional Dividend Plan	-0.89
4	Tata Equity Management	-0.17
5	JM Tax Gain Fund	0.14
6	JM Core 11 Fund	-0.51
7	Quantum Index Fund	-0.54
8	Tata Dividend Yield Fund	0.57
9	Tata Pure Equity Fund-Dividend Option	-0.53
10	Tata Ethical Fund-Dividend	0.16
11	Reliance Power Sector Fund - Institutional Dividend Plan	0.95
12	Quantum Liquid Fund	0.75
13	Quantum Long Term Equity Fund	-0.17
14	Reliance Retail Dividend Plan	0.20
15	Quantum Tax Saving Fund	0.18
16	Tata Equity Opportunities Fund-Dividend	0.22
17	Sundaram Equity Plus	0.83
18	Reliance Dual Advantage Fixed Tenure Fund Plan A - Dividend Plan	-0.78
19	Quantum Equity Fund Of Funds	0.30
20	JM Basic Fund	0.38
21	Max Life Smart Step Growth Fund	-0.45
22	JM Multi Strategy	-0.91
23	Sundaram Energy Opportunity Fund	.342
24	Sundaram Equity Multiplier	-0.21
25	JM Balanced Mutual	0.880

The above table reveals the correlation between market returns and fund returns. It is understood that there is positive correlation in case of 12 private sector funds. Negative correlation is found in case of 13 private sector funds.

VII RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Only two out of the five private sector balanced category mutual funds have earned a return above the average returns. Two firms have made negative returns. Amongst the private sector income schemes the maximum standard deviation is of TATA Income Fund at 18.74.

All the private sector balanced category funds selected for the study have a positive Sharpe ratio. The range of excess returns over risk-free return per unit of total risk is wide. All the funds selected for the study have a positive Treynor ratio. The range of excess returns over risk-free return per unit of systematic risk is wide. All the funds selected for the study has positive Jensen's alpha indicating superior performance.

There is positive correlation in case of 12 private sector funds between market returns and fund returns. Negative correlation is found in case of 13 private sector funds.

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